

Healthcare Beyond Reaction: Harnessing AI and Sensing for Proactive Care

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Abstract

As Artificial Intelligence (AI) and sensing technologies become embedded in daily life, their potential to transform care is undeniable. Yet, while these tools promise real-time insights, personalized interventions, and support for behavior change, their adoption seldom addresses the integration of people’s everyday care ecologies

and is limited by a focus on privacy, bias, and other ethical challenges. This means that AI-driven health interventions often fall short in proactive care, as they focus on improving *technical efficiency* but do not guarantee compatibility with *lived experiences* or provide *meaningful insights* into them. This workshop critically examines the roles of AI and sensing systems in health and wellbeing, adopting a human-centered perspective to enable proactive care. By convening researchers, designers, and practitioners from HCI, AI, health, and related fields, we will explore strategies to enhance the effectiveness of sensing and AI in proactive care. Our goal is to shape health technologies that prioritize accessibility, inclusivity, and alignment with users’ lived experiences, ensuring ethical and impactful innovations across diverse care contexts.

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CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Ubiquitous and mobile computing**; *Accessibility*; • **Information systems**; • **Applied computing** → **Life and medical sciences**;

Keywords

Sensing, Artificial Intelligence, Health and Wellbeing

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1 Introduction and Motivation

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Large Language Models (LLMs) are revolutionizing health and wellbeing by enabling real-time monitoring and innovative interventions [6, 19]. These technologies leverage sensor-driven systems and adaptive feedback mechanisms to improve health and its management [2]. AI-powered wearables, augmented reality/virtual reality (AR/VR) interventions, e.g., for stress reduction, and conversational agents are already in use for fitness tracking, stress reduction, and digital therapeutics [17]. LLMs are increasingly used in healthcare for tasks such as information mediation [5, 16, 27], medical documentation [7, 28], mental health support [11, 14, 15], and continuous health and wellbeing support [4, 11, 23]. However, despite rapid advances and new healthcare possibilities (such as facilitating a diagnostic journey by bridging a gap in clinical diagnosis [9]), AI-driven health technologies often fail to fully align with people’s needs, contextual realities, and ethical considerations, often raising critical concerns [21, 25].

Current research often emphasizes the application of AI rather than examining its meaningful impact on users. Many AI-driven health systems lack actionable personalization and contextual adaptation, limiting their ability to provide proactive support. Recent work [24] highlights the importance of aligning system capabilities with clinical practices and patient needs, underscoring the need to ground AI in real-world care contexts rather than offering generic, one-size-fits-all insights. Additionally, health AI is frequently used with fitness trackers, but analyses of physical metrics often overlook mental wellbeing and the qualitative, preventive insights necessary for supporting individuals holistically [6, 18, 21, 24, 28]. While AI interventions offer generic recommendations, they typically overlook users’ life circumstances [22], their preferences [8], disease progression [10], socio-economic factors [26], and cultural diversity. Doing so, AI risks reinforcing biases and failing to deliver equitable health benefits without a user-centered, interdisciplinary approach.

As AI expands into sensitive health contexts, addressing these gaps is crucial. This workshop, led by a diverse team, aims to integrate and incorporate diverse global healthcare perspectives, aligning with IH’s core themes. Designing adaptable AI-driven health systems that support diverse care ecosystems requires a holistic approach to ensure equitable access and real-world effectiveness.

While HCI research offers guidance, challenges remain in fully integrating AI and sensing technologies. Below, we outline the goals of the workshops in order to unpack and discuss the key healthcare AI challenges of: (1) Bridging Health Metrics with Actionable Insights; (2) Personalizing Insights Through Data Analysis while Reducing Bias; and (3) Sustaining Data-Driven User Engagement while Respecting Privacy and Ethics

2 Goals of the workshop

HCI conferences, such as CSCW and CHI, have explored AI in Health through panels, workshops, and SIGs covering AI in health has been examined through its design [3, 6], conversational agents [13], data-driven health solutions [12], HCI’s role in public health [1], and more [20]. As AI and health intersect, interdisciplinary collaboration is vital for mapping trends, identifying opportunities, and addressing integration challenges, which makes the Interactive Health Conference well-suited for this purpose. The goal of this workshop is to address the following key objectives:

- 1 **Explore the Meaningful Integration of Physical and Mental Health in AI Systems:** Investigate how AI-driven health technologies can incorporate mental and emotional wellbeing in a meaningful manner to the user alongside physical metrics. Discussions will cover the incorporation of care ecologies, multimodal sensing, data fusion, and adaptive interventions for a holistic, context-based approach to health.
- 2 **Identify Challenges and Ethical Considerations in AI-Driven Wellbeing Technologies:** Examine the barriers to effective AI integration in real-world healthcare, including bias, personalization, user engagement, and ethical risks. The workshop will focus on responsible AI design that considers diverse socio-economic and cultural contexts.
- 3 **Develop Strategies for Inclusive and Equitable AI-Driven Health Systems:** Foster interdisciplinary collaboration to design adaptable, context-aware AI solutions that ensure equitable access to health and wellbeing support. Discussions will draw from HCI insights, address global disparities, and promote user-centered, effective AI-driven interventions.

3 Workshop Structure, Organization, & Logistics

3.1 Plan to publish proceedings

The workshop details will be provided via a public website (such as beyondreaction.github.io), including the call for participation, the schedule (including the full program), the organizers, and the accepted papers, which will also be archived on Zenodo for free access and future research support. We will invite prospective attendees to submit posters (including position papers, work-in-progress research, and provocations) of up to 4 pages, excluding references. We are interested in a wide range of novel concepts and perspectives that support better utilization of AI and sensing for proactive care, aligned with diverse care realities. Workshop attendees will be selected to include diverse perspectives, backgrounds, and domains of expertise, based on the submissions received.

3.2 Prior to workshop

Before the workshop, participants will be encouraged to familiarize themselves with key challenges related to bridging the physical and mental health divide, personalizing insights, sustaining engagement, and addressing privacy and ethical concerns, particularly in the context of proactive care. Workshop candidates will also be invited to submit discussion topics and questions in advance, ensuring that the discussions are tailored to the community's needs and interests. A pre-workshop survey will collect information on attendees' expertise and areas of interest to further tailor the session's structure and discussions. Furthermore, an online session may be conducted, based on the results of the pre-workshop survey, to gather and finalize the workshop's discussion topics and interests.

3.3 Session Plan

This hybrid workshop will be a facilitated, interactive session (conducted via Zoom for online participants) that encourages real-time idea exchange, discussion, and collaboration. Participants will explore challenges in AI-driven health systems through open discussions, interdisciplinary problem-solving, and networking. Interactive activities, including brainstorming sessions and expert panels, will foster engagement, with initial insights shaping further exploration. Panelists from diverse domains will provide key perspectives, ensuring meaningful dialogue and collective action. All documents and recordings will be shared with the participants for asynchronous engagement. The accepted authors will also be required to present their posters in person after the first interactive session. The posters will be left up throughout the workshop session (with an online equivalent), allowing attendees to review them during the break if they missed them during the poster session. Table 1 outlines the tentative session plan.

3.4 Post workshop

After the workshop, we will summarize key discussions, takeaways, and proposed solutions, share them with attendees, and publish them on the workshop platform to encourage ongoing engagement. To maintain momentum, we will explore forming working groups around specific challenges, such as the ethical design of AI or personalization. Additionally, we will establish an online forum for ongoing discussion and resource sharing through Slack, promoting long-term collaboration among participants.

3.5 Organization

The organizers of this workshop come from diverse disciplines involving HCI, health, design, AI, policy, and applied computing. While some are academic researchers, we also have industrial practitioners doing translational research in the intersection of HCI, health, design, policy, and AI. Some organizers have prior experience running multiple successful workshops across various HCI conferences, including CHI, CSCW, DIS, and others, with a focus on health, HCI, and AI. The larger set of organizers is designed to accommodate online participation by attendees, synchronously with in-person presenters.

Shyama Sastha Krishnamoorthy Srinivasan is a final year PhD candidate at the Department of CSE, IIT-Delhi. His core thesis is the development of an HCAI Framework for *Collective Care*. His

work explores how AI and sensing technologies can be leveraged effectively to promote proactive health for collective care ecologies. Guided by minimalist design, his work aims to support users in achieving better health and wellbeing while being mindful of the costs involved.

Aisling Ann O'Kane is an Associate Professor of HCI for Health at the University of Bristol's Interaction Group (BIG). She researches the use and non-use of health, care, and wellbeing technologies outside of clinical settings, and how to design for real-world use with diverse users and contexts. She focuses on participatory approaches to AI design.

Ana Tajadura-Jiménez is an Associate Professor in the DEI Interactive Systems Group at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid and an Honorary Research Fellow at the UCL Interaction Centre. She leads the *i_mBODY* lab and is the Principal Investigator of the ERC-funded *BODYinTRANSIT* and the AEI-funded *SENSEBEAT-DS* projects, which explore sensory technologies for altering body perception, with a focus on emotional and physical health.

Anja Thieme is a Principal Researcher who co-leads the Teachable AI Experience (TAIX) team at Microsoft Research Cambridge. Her research focuses on human-centric approaches to designing innovative AI technology. She has extensive experience in healthcare, particularly in mental health and radiology. Driven by ethical and responsible AI principles, her work aims to enable personalized interventions, empower technology users, and promote greater equity and inclusion.

Farah Magrabi is a Professor of Biomedical and Health Informatics at the Australian Institute of Health Innovation, Macquarie University. She brings expertise in safe and responsible AI, serving as co-chair of the Australian AI Alliance's Working Group on safety, quality, and ethics. She has also made significant contributions to documenting the safety risks associated with digital technologies and AI in healthcare.

Francisco Nunes is a Senior Researcher at Fraunhofer Portugal AICOS, working on the human-centered Design team. His research focuses on the user research, design, and evaluation of mobile and AI-based self-care technologies.

Gautami Tripathi is an Assistant Professor at Jamia Hamdard University, Delhi, and a PhD candidate at the Department of CSE, IIT-Delhi. Her research intersects with HCI and Healthcare, focusing on COPD care in India by enhancing awareness, screening, diagnosis, and rehabilitation to foster proactive engagement among patients, caregivers, and healthcare professionals.

Kirti Lakra is a PhD candidate at the Department of CSE, IIT-Delhi. Her research integrates HCI, wearable sensors, VR, and ML/DL to enhance real-world EMG gesture recognition, with a focus on muscular fatigue challenges. She develops fatigue-resistant ML/DL techniques for more intuitive VR experiences.

Manshul Belani is an incoming post-doctoral researcher at Compliant & Accountable Systems Group, RC-Trust, University of Duisburg-Essen. Her doctoral research bridges HCI, VR, and education, emphasizing the effective design, development, and sustainable integration of VR Learning Environments (VRLEs) into standard curricula. She has also contributed to the development of assistive technologies for individuals with visual impairments, advancing inclusion.

Table 1: Proposed workshop schedule. *

Duration	Activity
30 minutes	Introductions: Welcome and general introductions to organizers, workshop objectives, and schedule, and an ice-breaker game.
60 minutes	Interactive Session: Thematic explorations on the Objectives of the workshop. Through provocations and ideation, teams will uncover benefits, drawbacks, and ethical implications for the three Challenges.
-	Break (engagement with posters at their convenience)
60 minutes	Author Posters Session: Authors move to the posters they put up before the session began to present their work. Organizers moderate the session as required.
-	Lunch (Themed groups, self-paid lunch with chosen Industry/Academia Mentors)
30 minutes	Author Posters Session: Poster interactions continue till afternoon session starts
60 minutes	Keynote: A 30-minute keynote presentation followed by 30 minutes Q&A with organizers moderating a brief expert panel, encouraging experts and participants to reflect on how the previous sessions influenced their understanding of the keynote.
-	Break (continued engagement with posters at their convenience)
60 minutes	Group Session: Groups will go through a set of interactive activities on Miro, prompting them to recall, reflect, and ideate on the work done in the previous session and how their cases and thoughts evolve in light of the discussion.
40 minutes	Summary Presentation: Each group presents and discusses the results of the ideation and mapping session with all other participants.
20 minutes	Wrap Up: Summarize the workshop, actions on follow-up activities, and group photos.
-	<i>Dinner and Social Events</i>

Mohan Kumar is a Professor of Computer Science at Rochester Institute of Technology. His research interests include pervasive and mobile computing and distributed systems. He co-advises PhD students at the intersection of HCAI and healthcare, focusing on health AI systems for collective care and emotion recognition.

Pragya Singh is a final year PhD candidate at the Department of CSE, IIT-Delhi. She researches wearable sensing, AI, and mental health, with a particular emphasis on human-centric data collection to enhance the reliability of Emotion Recognition Technology. She aims to develop more holistic personal mental health monitoring for everyday settings.

Pushpendra Singh is a Professor of Computer Science and Head of the Center of Excellence in Human-centered Computing at IIT-Delhi. His research interests are in Mobile Sensing, HCI, and ICT for Development. He has worked extensively in maternal and child health.

Sara Moin is a PhD candidate at the Department of CSE, IIT-Delhi. Her research focuses on developing technologies for women's health in the Indian context. She designs solutions that empower women through advocacy and improved health literacy on intimate health, using interdisciplinary research and HCAI to drive meaningful change.

Vedant Das Swain is an Assistant Professor in the Department of Technology Management and Innovation at New York University. His research focuses on transforming digital applications, behavioral models, and infrastructures to enhance workers' behavioral

health. Dr. Das Swain aims to build digital work technologies to support wellbeing and promote healthier performance by mitigating invisible labor, emotional fatigue, and burnout.

3.6 Audience, Engagement, Outreach & Logistics

This workshop is designed for graduate students, researchers, designers, practitioners, and stakeholders in AI-driven health systems, including experts from healthcare, UX design, AI, behavioral sciences, ethics, and HCI. It fosters interdisciplinary collaboration to develop inclusive, ethical, and sustainable AI health solutions. The workshop aims to attract 35–50 participants (≤ 50 posters) through professional networks, CHI mailing lists, and social media platforms. The dedicated website will outline the objectives, agenda, and invited experts, and link to the main conference site. Several researchers have already committed to promoting attendance.

4 Call for Participation

As AI, LLMs, and sensing technologies (including wearables, mobile sensors, AR/VR, and environmental monitors) become integrated into everyday life, they hold enormous potential to shift healthcare from reactive fixes to proactive support. Yet many AI-driven health systems still fall short of delivering meaningful, equitable, and contextually relevant benefits to real people. To surface practical directions, design approaches, strategies, and critical reflections to improve the effectiveness of AI and sensing for proactive care, we invite researchers, designers, clinicians, industry practitioners,

policy-makers, and community stakeholders to participate in the workshop: *Healthcare Beyond Reaction: Harnessing AI and Sensing for Proactive Care*.

The workshop will be held as a one-day hybrid interactive session at IH'26, with the goals of identifying design opportunities, surfacing deployment challenges, and fostering interdisciplinary collaborations for proactive healthcare systems. We invite researchers, designers, clinicians, industry practitioners, policymakers, and community partners to submit posters (including short position papers, design posters, work-in-progress, or provocations (PDF, ≤ 4 pages single column ACM Submission Template excluding references) that explore AI/LLMs, sensing, personalization, explainability, ethics, evaluation, and socio-technical governance for proactive, equitable health and care systems. Submissions will be reviewed for relevance, clarity, novelty, and potential to enrich interdisciplinary dialogue.

Accepted authors will present posters (for in-person participants) and participate in interactive sessions during the workshop, which focuses on practical design and deployment challenges. Accepted submissions will be published on the workshop website for open access (as well as Zenodo). In addition to the authors of submissions, the workshop will also be open to online attendees who wish to participate in activities. The online portion will be moderated via Zoom. At least one author of each accepted submission must attend to present the poster, and all participants must register for the workshop through IH'26. Submit your poster via workshop website (see site for deadlines and submission details) —questions? email hcbeeyondreaction@gmail.com

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